

Session Script - Participatory Design Fiction

Starting the session

- Remembering the terms of the consent form.
- Explaining research objectives.
- Asking permission for recording.
- Sending the link to the fictional story [animated video]

How should the super bot act in the following situations? Please, detail your answers as much as possible.

1. When a newcomer submits a contribution to an open-source project.
2. When a core developer is working on a priority task. (*when a core developer works on something and doesn't want to get interrupted*)
3. When one or more bots are inflating the pull requests with repetitive or verbose information.
4. When a bot performs an unsolicited action on a pull request because of a bug or spam.

Followed by (if needed):

- *What is the most important feature in this case?*
- *What should this super bot not do in this case?*
- *How do you think the super bot would manage the action and information generated by other bots?*

Wrap-up questions:

- **What else do you think the super bot will be capable of doing to avoid the noise? Give an example.**